

IMPACT OF COVID-19 AND EMPLOYEES REACTION TO CHANGES ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE OF BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

Significant changes in how service firms function, influencing staff routines and activities, are referred to as COVID-19 prevalence. Covid-19, also known as corona virus or corona virus, was originally discovered in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and is known as "2019-nCoV." (BBC, 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) recognized Covid-19 as a new corona virus that presents a threat to world health on February 11, 2020. It exhibits the same characteristics as previous corona virus pandemics (SARS and MERS), but its source is unknown (Zhao et al., 2020: 215). Covid-19 has been dubbed a "pandemic" because of its rapid spread over the globe, signifying a global pandemic (BBC, 2020). Bangladesh's economy is in shambles as a result of the corona virus. Bangladesh began opening its business sector in May 2020 in order to preserve the economy. To mitigate the effect of corona virus, the government has implemented "new normal" guidelines for businesses. The primary goals of this research are to determine how the Covid-19 pandemic has influenced employee performance and to determine the workers' perspectives regarding the changes that have been made to their everyday lives as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic scenario in Bangladesh. To complete this research, employee performance was assessed using the 'Employee Response to Change (ERC)' method. Employees from many sectors have been studied. For this research, 300 people from various sectors were surveyed online at random. The study was quantitative as well as exploratory. It was based solely on original data. The research used a non-probability sampling approach to collect data. The survey questionnaire was sent to those who replied via a Google form. Results and visual representations are found using SPSS and Microsoft Excel. COVID-19 and the reaction to employee changes have a considerable detrimental influence on employee performance, according to all of the study's findings. The employee's focus, communication, and attention to work are all adversely affected by these "new normal" alterations.

Keywords: Covid-19, Employees Reaction, Employee Performance, Employee changes, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Great crises have struck humanity at various periods, affecting all cultures. Depression and crises such as war, natural disasters (famines, earthquakes, fires, climate change, and so on), pandemics, economic crises, terrorist activities, and political conflicts have all been mentioned as causes of these major fissures, and the world as a consequence has changed

profoundly. The whole society is affected. Unfortunately, the present situation, which has been exacerbated by the Covid-19 outbreak, is a global depression, which might result in a big calamity. Pandemics, which have a lengthy history, have found new sites to spread in a short amount of time as a consequence of societal interaction, resulting in a large number of deaths (thousands or maybe millions) that would not have happened otherwise. The demise of big states-empires has already been seen (Ylmaz, 2007: 27).

Covid-19, also known as corona virus or corona virus, was originally discovered in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and is known as "2019-nCoV." (BBC, 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) recognized Covid-19 as a new kind of corona virus that presents a threat to world health on February 11, 2020. It exhibits many of the same characteristics as previous corona virus outbreaks (SARS and MERS), but its source is unclear (Zhao et al., 2020: 215). Covid-19 has been dubbed a "pandemic" because of its rapid spread over the globe, signifying a global pandemic (BBC, 2020).

More than 200,000 new cases were reported every day throughout the globe. Despite the fact that there were 8,919,225 closed cases, the restored planet still faces a significant struggle. Because of the 'new normal' rule, anything will be expected, which is wonderful for business but terrible for health protection. During the COVID-19 epidemic, all firms were compelled to cease normal operations and commence formal work utilizing technology to digitize processes.

In line with the new political and social laws, emergency action plans, such as working from home, have been implemented (Ince, F., 2020). The firm had a tremendous challenge in controlling the Covid-19 outbreak and its impact on workers. The current concern is worker safety and performance (Carnevale et al., 2020).

Employees are said to be stressed as a result of the present environment of fear and uncertainty, which lowers their productivity. This is because individuals who work under stress are physically and mentally unable to engage in their tasks. As a consequence, someone who is working under stress because of a fear of Covid-19 is unlikely to perform well.

1.1 Defining the issue

Bangladesh believes that Covid-19 came to Bangladesh a bit too soon. With a population of 164,689,383 inhabitants, Bangladesh is a small nation (Worldmeters.info, 2020). The first three instances were detected in Bangladesh on March 3, 2020, according to Wikipedia. On March 23, 2020, Bangladesh, like many other countries, declared a state of emergency. The number of instances of covid-19 in Bangladesh has risen dramatically since then. Bangladesh has reported a total of 199,357 fatalities, 108,725 recoveries, and 2,547 deaths as on July 17, 2020. According to Nazila Fathi's article in the International Finance Corporation, Bangladesh is known for its garment industry (IFC). Bangladesh is the second-largest exporter of apparel in the world.

According to npr.org's Lauren Frere, the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in the layoff of over 1 million garment workers. Similar concerns have arisen in other businesses, including

as the Covid-19 epidemic, which resulted in wage terminations, delayed pay, and temporary employment. As a consequence of the COVID-19 outbreak, Bangladeshi businesses, like those in other nations, have been compelled to close their doors and conduct official business from their homes (once, F., 2020). Employees who need to produce work, give customer service, or work in a bank, however, must be physically active (Wang B. et al., 2020). Bangladesh, like the majority of countries, employs the same 'new normal' to increase job opportunities and protect companies' and workers' interests.

1.2 Research Issues

Based on the given data, the following are the objectives:

RQ1: Does Covid-19 have an effect on the performance of employees in Bangladesh?

RQ2: Does an employee's response to a change affect their performance?

1.3 The study's purpose

The primary goals of this research are to determine how the Covid-19 has impacted employee performance.

RO1: To determine how workers feel about the changes made to their everyday lives as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak.

1.4 The study's limitation

The goal of this study is to investigate how employees respond to the "new normal" and how it impacts their productivity. As a consequence, the conclusions of this research had certain limitations.

Due of the COVID-19 epidemic, there was an inadequate reaction.

Employee attitudes and responses to organizational changes have received comparatively little study, making comparisons difficult. The influence of changes to the "new normal" on employee performance was investigated in this research.

1.5 The Study's scope

In the future, employee reactions to change might be evaluated by evaluating openness to change and change support. While this research did not concentrate on a specific organization, future studies may choose to do so in order to get more accurate results. The COVID-19 investigation must be carried out with every possible outcome in mind.

2. Review of the Literature

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented a significant danger to the whole world. Both income and security are strained as a result of this pandemic. All firms must forsake their old routines and adopt a new way of communicating and directing their everyday operations. In this circumstance, managers must make critical choices in order to protect the interests of

their companies and their people (Van D. M. et al., 2017; Van Z. & Van D. M., 2015). Things start to stabilize in June or July, but we still have to cope with COVID-19.

Personnel in manufacturing, banking, customer service, and any other sector requiring direct communication were impeded by Covid-19. The most dangerous condition for these employees on the globe. COVID-19 has also had an influence on education (Wang C. et al., 2020). It's not always simple to work from home. Managing work also requires caring for families and children, which may lead to role conflicts. The staff's overall performance has been impacted by these concerns. To ensure worker safety, the government mandated that masks, body distance, hand washing, and hand sanitizer be used everywhere in the workplace (Woloret.al.,2020). Wolor and colleagues (Wolor et al., 2020). Employee performance is affected by their emotional state as well. Workers were especially worried about their safety during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Hamouche, stress and despair have the greatest impact on employees' mental health (2020). Employees' top worries are safety, infection risk, social isolation, financial loss, and job stability. Employee stress and poor performance at work are mostly caused by these factors.

According to Sasaki Atoll, employee health, social distance, financial stability, employment security, stress reduction, and better staff performance are all top goals for the organization (2020). Hasanat et al. looked at the effects of COVID-19 on e-commerce (2020). According to this assessment, owing to their restricted consumer base, the pandemic has had a major effect on small and medium-sized shops. Consumer buying behaviour has been significantly influenced by the novel corona virus.

A corona virus may harm small businesses, as well as industry, education, and other sectors. COVID-19 has had a worldwide influence on a wide range of businesses. As a consequence of this, the economy is suffering. The world, on the other hand, cannot continue in this fashion. Everything is starting to open up, and firms are getting ready for actual work under the new rules.

Working from home and digitizing the workplace was a great notion during Covid-19, but it didn't endure long due of digital inequality. Working on the COVID-19 problem and digital disparities, Beaunoyer Elisabeth et al. (2020) stated that inequalities are produced by variances in technology, ethnicity, and discrepancies among other workers. Employees in rural or remote areas will be unable to handle home chores since they will not have access to the most up-to-date internet. During the home time, interruptions from family members will cause the job to be disturbed. The employee's performance under COVID-19 was poorer than in the previous COVID-19 condition, according to F. (2020). COVID-19 has pushed employees to work from home, which has had a significant effect on productivity. As a consequence, worker performance decreased during the COVID-19 outbreak.

2.1 COVID-19

The Corona virus has forced people all across the world to remain inside (Ahmed, 2020). Hasnat et al. (2020) claim that COVID-19 has the largest influence on the industry, resulting in a significant decline in product imports and exports. No import-export does not suggest a

difficult-to-manufacture company or high-risk direct communication job. Production has already been suspended, with those who undertake this work feeling the brunt of the effects. Most nations open their companies and begin production in June or July under the 'new normal' guideline. However, COVID-19 is still there, thus performance is crucial (Wang B. et al., 2020). Because COVID-19 has an influence on employee performance at all levels, it was selected as one of the study's independent variables. Due of digital injustice, family-work conflicts, stress, and sleep concerns, COVID-19 forced enterprises to work from home, which proved ineffectual.

Despite the fact that everything has started to follow the 'new normal' rule, COVID-19 (Bernard, 2020, Beauvais Elizabeth et al., 2020) and fear remain.

2.2. Reactions and Changes

Employees may be synchronized with new organizational changes in a number of ways. Why is it vital to change employee feedback as the company grows? Employees will be stressed, and their production will be harmed as a result. As a consequence of work-from-home arrangements, workers are worried about the COVID-19 pandemic, the corona virus, and work-family disputes (Van D. et al., 2018). Employee responses to a business change must be dealt with by a strong leader. Change, as well as individual change preparedness and commitment, are all aspects of employee engagement.

To keep workers involved in change, a leader must serve as a change agent. A leader must cultivate employee happiness in order to create a positive reaction to change. One of a leader's most precious assets is his ability to convince his followers to accept new advances. It is vital to investigate the stress and well-being of employees in the workplace in order to modify this (Mangundajaya et al., 2015; Tyler et al., 2005). The COVID-19 vaccine will be available in July 2020. However, the globe must go ahead in order to rescue the economy.

To keep everything on track, the world follows the 'new normal' guideline. What precisely is the "new normal"? Outside, you should constantly wear a mask, use a sensitizer, wash your hands often, operate from home, maintain a social distance of at least 2 meters, and check your temperature for fever, according to The Starting. Employees are constantly challenged with change. Employees must accept things, whether they like it or not, since they are unfamiliar to them and must be followed for health reasons. A study of employee behaviour, according to Men et al., impacts any company change (2020). Also, propose that you build trust with corporate employees before adopting changes. Firms are implementing new norms and standards to decrease infection and improve personal hygiene awareness, according to another research, since employee confidence influences employee willingness to organizational changes.

As a consequence, the response to changes was selected as an independent variable in this research. Employees have opinions on how the firm is doing. This might affect their performance in a favourable or bad way.

2.3 Employee Performance

Employee performance is affected by the fear of catching the corona virus, whether they work from home or not. We avoid several activities, including travelling to the hospital, since we are afraid of contracting corona virus from corona virus-positive people. It's understandable to be worried about the corona virus spreading unnoticed. Using 'new normal' criteria, however, it is possible to reduce the risk. To alleviate employee stress and anxiety, all businesses are implementing these measures.

Employees will be able to perform better at work since they will not be afraid (Solis et al., 2020). Employee performance is influenced by a variety of factors. Ms. J. Suja Kanu et al. (2020) looked at the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours of the Indian food sector. To function effectively, employees must be informed of COVID-19. Employees must be informed of safety measures, positive about changing their attitudes, and, eventually, follow safety protocols to reduce corona virus risks. The company mandates employee safety measurement training.

Workers will be subjected to this training on a regular basis to learn how to use social distance and masks. As a consequence, employees will feel more at ease in the workplace (Das, 2020). Because COVID-19 is considered as the deadliest virus, companies were forced to lock down and impose new ideas in order to continue functioning from home. However, it has been seen that as a consequence of their labor, employees' performance has declined.

Working from home is a great method to reduce stress while still meeting formal obligations. It does, however, have certain limitations. Employee performance is impacted by depression, work-family conflict, digital injustice, stress, and the reality that not all work can be done from home (Carin et al., 2020; Wang C. et al., 2020). These issues, along with cybercrime, home network hacking, and identity theft, are serious problems (Ahmad, 2020). As a consequence, workers' dread of the corona virus makes it difficult for them to maintain their work and home performance.

Since May 2020, many firms throughout the world, including Bangladesh, have been working under the 'new normal.' Workers are beginning to labour physically all around the globe.

The challenge now is to protect the safety of the personnel while yet completing the assignment (Woloret.al. 2020, Sasaki et.al., 2020). Employee performance has worsened as a consequence of the increased criteria. The post-Covidien scenario, according to that source, will also be uncommon.

The challenge now is how the company can increase staff productivity amid the pandemic. According to Sasaki et al., (2020), mental health must be maintained to increase employee performance by minimizing fear and anxiety with Covid-19. Furthermore, the research suggests that an employee's mental wellness may influence their performance.

2.4 Framework for Research

The goal of this research is to see whether there's a link between Corona virus (COVID-19) and employee performance and how they respond to changes. As a consequence, based on the related concepts and studies mentioned in this research, a hypotheses model has been developed to examine these links.

Figure 1: Hypotheses Model of Impact of Corona virus (COVID-19) and Employee's Reaction to Changes on Employee Performance.

In this hypotheses model, we can see that two components are independent and have a direct relationship with the dependent factor, employee performance. The hypothesis is prepared to assist the researcher in meeting the study's objectives.

- **H1.** Covid19 has a major influence on the performance of employees.
- **H2.** Employees' responses to changes have a big influence on their productivity.

3. Methodology

The approach employed in the research project study is described in this chapter. It contains details on the study design, research instrument, data collecting, and data analysis procedures used to assess this project.

3.1 Research Methodology

The "Employee Performance Model" was employed in this investigation. Studies are carried out to identify a previous or present state, according to the survey model. The relational survey model was utilized in the study, which is one of the survey models in the general survey category. The model in question is made up of data pairings that may be used to do a relational analysis (Karasar, 2020: 114). The research was both quantitative and exploratory in nature. It was entirely based on original data. For the aim of data gathering, the research used a non-probability sampling strategy.

The study's main goal was to determine the impact of the Corona virus (COVID-19) and employees' reactions to changes on Bangladeshi employee performance. Finally, based on the literature research and questionnaire survey, a content analysis was undertaken.

3.2 The study's population

The population of this research covers all workers in the city of Dhaka.

3.3 The study's sample size

The study's sample consisted of 200 such workers who filled out a Google form to participate in the survey.

3.4 Research Methodology

To achieve the main goal of this study, descriptive research was done. Three components of a self-administered questionnaire were created. The influence of covid-19 on workers' workplaces, employees' reactions to these changes, and how these changes affect their job performance were all covered in the survey. The questionnaire's answers were calculated using a five-point Likert scale. S.A stands for Strongly Agree, A for Agree, N for Neutral, D for Disagree, and S.D stands for Strongly Disagree, with numbers ranging from 1 to 5.

3.5 Data Gathering

The information is gathered from a number of sources and ways. The two most frequent categories of information are primary and secondary sources. The survey was largely conducted online using Google Forms, which allowed for an endless number of respondents. This survey was sent through Face book to key figures, and secondary data was acquired via a literature review.

3.6 Data Analysis Methodologies

Following the collection of survey data, the study analysis commenced. The demographic analysis of the respondents, descriptive statistics for all factors, factor reliability analysis, factor analysis, and regression analysis using SPSS-26 are all used in this project's data analysis. The findings of the survey data analysis are reported in the next section of the study.

4. Examine the Data

This title presents and discusses the comprehensive information gathered from the questionnaire survey in order to demonstrate the study purpose. This chapter is divided into five sections:

Demographic Analysis of Respondents Descriptive Statistics of All Factors, Factor Reliability Analysis, Pearson Correlation Analysis of All Factors, and Factor Regression Analysis.

4.1 Demographic Analysis of Respondents

As part of the current investigation, a survey was undertaken. The survey is done among workers across Dhaka city, with a total sample size of 200 (n = 200). Demographic characteristics of respondents comprised gender, age group, marital status, highest educational level, and employment. Tables 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 provide the following information:

Table 4.1: Gender data analysis

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	123	61.5
Female	77	38.5
Total	200	100.0

This table clearly illustrates that male employees are more likely to participate than female employees. There are 123 male workers (61.5%) and 77 female employees (38.5%) in this study's sample size of 200 participants.

Table 4.2: Age data analysis

Age Group	Frequency	Percent
20 years or below	9	4.5
21 – 30 years	88	44.0
31 – 40 years	84	42.0
41 – 50 years	19	9.5
Total	200	100.0

Employees of all ages are present. We can see from the table that the majority of respondents are between the ages of 21 and 30, accounting for 88 (44.0 percent) of the total. Second is the age group of 31-40 years, with 84 (42.0 percent) respondents, followed by the age group of 41-50 years, with 19 (9.5 percent) respondents, and the age group of 20 years or less, with 9 (4.5 percent) respondents.

Table 4.3: Marital Status data analysis

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	111	55.5
Married	89	44.5
Total	200	100.0

This table clearly demonstrates that the number of single workers outnumbers the number of married employees. There are 111 single workers (55.5 percent) and 89 married employees (44.5 percent) in this study's total sample size of 200 respondents.

Table 4.4: Highest Educational Level data analysis

Highest Educational Level	Frequency	Percent
Certificate	12	6.0
Diploma	11	5.5
Matric	12	6.0
Postgraduate Degree	76	38.0
University Degree	89	44.5
Total	200	100.0

The occupation level group of Private Ltd. Employees has the biggest number of responses in this table. They account for 32.5 percent of the overall sample and 65 people. With 57 replies, or 28.5 percent, the second biggest category is an executive group. They discovered that 53 (26.5%) of the respondents are government employees. Businessmen account for 11 (5.5%) of the total number of responders, while professionals account for 9 (4.5%). Lecturers account for 5 (2.5 percent) of the total number of responders.

Table 4.5: Occupation data analysis

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Private Ltd. Employee	65	32.5
Lecturer	5	2.5
Govt. Employee	53	26.5
Professional	9	4.5
Executive	57	28.5
Businessman	11	5.5
Total	200	100.0

4.2 Respondents' Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.6: Descriptive Analysis for Each Variable

Variables	Total Mean	Standard Deviation
Impact of Covid-19	4.087	0.30
Employees Reactions to Changes	4.075	0.36
Employee Performance	4.010	0.47

The descriptive statistics of the variables in the research are shown in Table 4.6. With a value of 4.0857, the Impact of Covid-19 has the highest mean. Employee Reactions to Changes in Use came in second with a score of 4.0785, while employee performance came in third with a score of 4.0100. According to the findings, the majority of respondents agree with the assertion that the value of the mean is more than 3.

4.3 Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Analysis

Table 4.7 demonstrates that all variables had a Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.70, which is considered acceptable. Employee performance with 5 items had the greatest Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.837, followed by Impact of Covid-19 with a value of 0.745 and Employees Reactions to Changes with a value of 0.732. As a consequence of the reliability testing, it was determined that the items utilized in the research for each variable were in fact consistent.

Table 4.7: Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Verdict
Impact of Covid-19	0.745	15	Acceptable
Employees Reactions to Changes	0.732	10	Acceptable
Employee Performance	0.837	5	Acceptable

4.4 Pearson Correlation Analysis

Table 4.8: Pearson Correlation Analysis

		Impact of Covid19	Employee Reaction to Changes	Employee performance
Impact of Covid 19	Pearson Correlation	1	0.591**	0.413**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	200	200	200
Employee Reaction to Changes	Pearson Correlation	0.591**	1	0.489**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	200	200	200
Employee performance	Pearson Correlation	0.413**	0.489**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
	N	200	200	200
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

As indicated in Table 4.8, there is a substantial, moderate relationship between Impact of Covid19 and employee performance ($r = 0.413$, $P 0.01$). Employee Reaction to Changes has a significant, moderate link with employee performance ($r = 0.489$, $P 0.01$), but it also has a significant, moderate relationship with employee performance ($r = 0.489$, $P 0.01$).

4.5 Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is done to examine the simultaneous effects of several independent variables on a dependent variable that is interval scaled. In this study we have done regression analysis to find out the significant and positivity in Impact of Covid-19 on employees' performance. The regression analysis has been shown below in table 4.9, 4.10 and 4.11

Table 4.9: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.595 ^a	0.417	0.409	0.41380
a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee_ Reaction_ to_ Changes, Impact_of_Covid19				
b. Dependent Variable: Employee_ performance				

Here the model summary via regression analysis, it has been found that the R-squared value is $R^2 = 0.417$. So according to the equation ($1-R^2 = e_i$) error term we found in the study is 0.538 ($1-0.417 = 0.538$).

The ANOVA test is used to demonstrate that our research is significant for the positive and direct association between Covid-19's impact on employee performance. The ANOVA test table 4.10 clearly reveals that the study's regression analysis result is significant.

Table 4.10: ANOVA test of Regression Analysis

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	10.967	2	5.484	32.0	.000 ^b
Residual				25	
Total	33.733	197	.171		
	44.700	199			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee_ performance					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee_ Reaction_ to_ Changes, Impact_of_Covid19					

Furthermore, we can now assert that employee performance is significant.

Table 4.11: Coefficients Results of Employee performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Impact of Covid19	0.289	0.058	0.320	4.959	0.000
Employee Reaction to Changes	0.393	0.085	0.299	4.637	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance

The findings of the coefficients of variables affecting customer impression are shown in this table. Where we can plainly see that all components Impact of Covid19, Employee Reaction to Changes, and Employee Performance have a significant link with Employee performance since their significance result is less than 0.05.

4.6 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4.12: Hypothesis Testing

	Hypothesis	Remarks
H ₁	Covid19 has a significant impact on employee's performance.	Supported
H ₂	Employee's reaction to changes has a significant impact on employee's performance.	Supported

Impact of covid-19 has a substantial link with employee performance, according to research ($\beta = 0.320$, $p = 0.000$ 0.01). Employees' reactions to changes have a substantial impact on their performance ($\beta = 0.299$, $p = 0.000$ 0.05). As a result, both hypotheses are valid.

5. Discussion

Based on the findings of the analysis, it can be concluded that the COVID-19 epidemic has had a substantial impact on Bangladeshi employee performance. Employee performance is suffering as a result of the corona virus. COVID-19's influence on employee performance has been assessed via workplace behavior, communication methods, everyday activities and social distance (table 4.12, 4.13, 4.14, 4.15, 4.16).

- **H1a: COVID-19 has affected the behavior of employees during performing works.**

Table 4.13: Descriptive for Behavior in Workplace.

	N	Mean	Level of agreement
Behavior in Workplace	200	4.1070	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	200		

A significant number of employees highly agreed that COVID-19 has affected the behavior of employees during performing work and most of the employees agreed with a mean value of 4.1071.

- **H1b: COVID-19 has a significant impact on the way of communication.**

Table 4.14: Descriptive for Way of Communication.

	N	Mean	Level of agreement
Way of Communications	200	4.0420	Highly Agree
Valid N (listwise)	200		

Covid-19 may be passed from person to person in an unsafe interaction. To reduce risk, businesses prohibit direct conversion. Superior employees are permitted to work from home and interact with coworkers and subordinates using digital technology. With a mean score of 4.0420, the majority of workers strongly agreed that COVID-19 had an influence on their communication style.

- **H1c: Covid19 has a significant impact on daily activities.**

Table 4.15: Descriptive for Daily Activities.

	N	Mean	Level of agreement
Daily Activities	200	4.1080	Highly Agree
Valid N (list wise)	200		

COVID-19 has had a considerable influence on the majority of workers' everyday operations. With a mean score of 4.1080, COVID-19 has adjusted their everyday behaviors by adding washing hands, wearing a mask, and limiting handling items in the workplace. Social alienation, the wearing of masks, and the writing down of personal information are all examples of the 'new normal'. This study employs social distance and the usage of masks to assess employees' responses to changes.

- **H2a: Social Distancing has significant impact on work performance.**

Table 4.16: Descriptive for Social Distancing.

	N	Mean	Level of agreement
Social Distancing	200	4.0300	Highly Agree
Valid N (list wise)	200		

One of the most significant changes in the workplace is social alienation. With a mean score of 4.0300, the majority of workers strongly believe that social alienation has a considerable influence on their job performance. Production-oriented professions, marketing positions with a lot of direct engagement, and social distancing all cause a contradiction between duties and safety measurements.

- **H2b: Use of mask during communication affects daily work outcome.**

Table 4.17: Descriptive for Using Mask.

	N	Mean	Level of agreement
Using Mask	200	4.1270	Highly Agree
Valid N (listwise)	200		

With a mean score of 4.1270, the majority of workers strongly agreed that wearing masks interfered with their communication while completing job at the company. Employees have discovered that these adjustments are interfering with their regular job effectiveness.

5.1 Findings

We showed five analyses in the previous chapter of data analysis: demographic frequency analysis, where male employee involvement is higher than female employee participation. There are 123 male workers (61.5 percent) and 77 female employees (38.5 percent) in this study's total sample size of 200 respondents. The majority of respondents are between the ages of 21 and 30, accounting for 88 (44.0%) of the total. Second is the age group of 31-40 years, with 84 (42.0 percent) respondents, followed by the age group of 41-50 years, with 19 (9.5 percent) respondents, and the age group of 20 years or less, with 9 (4.5 percent) respondents. Employees who are single outnumber those who are married. There are 111 single workers (55.5%) and 89 married employees (44.5%) in this study's sample size of 200 respondents. University graduates make up the largest group of responders. There were 89 people in all, accounting for 44.5 percent of the entire sample size. With 38.0 percent of the overall sample size, 76 respondents have a postgraduate degree. This demonstrates that the sample was typical of the study's target group of educated workers.

Following in sequence, the Certificate and Metric levels contain 12 responders each, accounting for 6.0 percent of the overall sample size. Apart from these 11 Diploma-level respondents (5.5%), there were no other respondents. The Private Ltd. Employee category of profession level had the biggest number of responders. They account for 32.5 percent of the overall sample and 65 people. With 57 replies, or 28.5 percent, the second biggest category is an executive group. They discovered that 53 (26.5%) of the respondents are government employees. Businessmen account for 11 (5.5%) of the overall number of respondents, while professionals account for 9 (4.5%). Lecturers account for 5 (2.5%) of the total number of respondents.

The Impact of Covid-19 had the greatest mean in the descriptive analysis, with a value of 4.0857. Employee Reactions to Changes in Use came in second with a score of 4.0785, while employee performance came in third with a score of 4.0100. According to the findings, the majority of respondents agree with the states where the value of the mean can be demonstrated to be more than 3.

All variables have a Cronbach's alpha above 0.70, which is acceptable in reliability analysis. Employee performance with 5 items had the highest Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.745, followed by Impact of Covid-19 with a value of 0.745, and Employees Reactions to Changes with a value of 0.732. As a consequence of this reliability testing, it was determined that the items utilized in the research for each variable were in fact consistent.

There is a significant, moderate connection in Pearson's correlation with; a significant association between the Impact of Covid19 and employee performance ($r = 0.413$, $P 0.01$). While there is a substantial, moderate association between Employee Reaction to Changes and employee performance ($r = 0.489$, $P 0.01$), there is also a significant, moderate relationship between Employee Reaction to Changes and employee performance ($r = 0.489$, $P 0.01$).

The R-squared value was discovered to be $R^2 = 0.417$ in regression analysis. As a result, the error term observed in the research ($1-R^2 = ei$) is 0.538 ($1-0.417 = 0.538$). The ANOVA test is used to demonstrate that our research is significant for the positive and direct association between Covid-19's impact on employee performance. The outcome of the regression analysis for the research is significant, as shown in Table 4.10 of the ANOVA test. Furthermore, we can now assert that employee performance is significant. Whereas all components have an impact on Covid19, Employee Reaction to Changes has a substantial link with Employee Performance, with a significance result of less than 0.05. Wherever we looked, we found that all of the analyses had favorable and substantial outcomes.

5.2 Conclusion

We may deduce that these 'new normal' alterations were implemented for health and safety reasons. To safeguard the economy, Bangladesh has reopened practically every commercial sector. In Bangladesh, the Corona virus is rapidly spreading. To lessen the effect of corona virus, the government should enact these steps. These precautions are usually taken to limit the risk of corona virus. It is tough to keep a busy schedule since these changes are new to individuals in the workplace. Employees must accept these changes as a result of the epidemic, but their responses and sentiments about them prohibit them from focusing entirely on their job as they did before. Employees will need extra time to adjust to the changes in the "new normal."

As a result, the government enforces 'new normal' guidelines that everyone must obey in order to decrease the danger. Employees must accept new rules or adjustments when they are placed on a company. Employees agree and disagree on a regular basis. However, it is critical to track their emotions and responses. This is because if the employee has a negative response to the change, it may become a performance barrier.

Apart from the pandemic, there have been other changes in companies, and leaders may take the initiative to maintain and manage employees in accordance with the changes, or even include workers in the changes.

5.3 Theoretical and practical implications

In the future, employee reactions to change might be evaluated by evaluating openness to change and change support. While this research did not concentrate on a specific organization, future studies may choose to do so in order to get more accurate results. The COVID-19 investigation must be carried out with every possible outcome in mind. This paper will assist businesses and future researchers in gaining a better knowledge of covid-19, as well as its influence and behavioral changes on workers and their everyday performance.

References

- [1] Beaunoyer E. D., Sophie G, Matthieu J., (2020). COVID-19 and digital inequalities: Reciprocal impacts and mitigation strategies. *Computers in Human Behavior* 111 (2020) 106424.
- [2] Bernard & Nkala, (2020). A Reflection on the implementation of flexible working hours on public health service delivery during coronavirus (COVID-19) era in Zimbabwe: The survey for the nursing professionals employed at Parirenyatwa group of hospitals. *International Journal of Advanced Research*.
- [3] Carnevale, Joel B. Hatak & Isabella, (2020). Employee adjustment and well-being in the era of COVID-19: Implications for human resource management. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 116, Issue May, Pages 183-187.
- [4] Covid-19 Pandemic, information of corona cases, Available at: <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>
- [5] Covid-19 Pandemic in Bangladesh. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID19_pandemic_in_Bangladesh.
- [6] Craig William, (2018). The importance of creating sustainable employees in the workplace. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/williamcraig/2018/06/19/the-importance-of-creating-sustainable-employees-in-the-workplace/>
- [7] Das A, (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the workflow of an ambulatory endoscopy center: an assessment by discrete event simulation, *Gastrointestinal Endoscopy*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gie.2020.06.008>.
- [8] Eliza W., Kin-fai H., Samuel W., Annie C., Eng-kiong Y., (2020). Workplace safety and coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic: survey of employees. *Bull World Health Organ*. E-pub: 20th March 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2471/BLT.20.255893>
- [9] Fathi N., (2020). 'Safety first: Bangladesh Garment Industry Rebound'. Available at: https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/news_ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/news+and+events/news/insights/bangladesh-garment-industry.
- [10] Hamouche, S, (2020). COVID-19 and employees' mental health: stressors, moderators and agenda for organizational actions. *Emerald Open Research*, Volume 2.
- [11] Hasanat, Mohammad W, Ashikul S., Farzana A., Mashrekha, Abdul H., Abu B. & Huam, (2020). The Impact of Coronavirus (Covid-19) on E-Business in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* Vol. 3, No. 1, (2020) ISSN 2651-6691 (Print) ISSN 2651-6705 (Online).

- [12] İnce, F., (2020). The Effects of Covid-19 Pandemic On the Workforce In Turkey. *International Social Mentality and Researcher Thinkers Journal*, (Issn:2630-631X) 6(32): 1125-1134.
- [13] Laura F., (2020). The CoronaVirus crisis. Available at: <https://www.npr.org/sections/coronavirus-live-updates/2020/04/03/826617334/1-millionbangladeshi-garment-workers-lose-jobs-amid-covid-19-economic-fallout>.
- [14] Juan R., Cen A. &Yonghong L., (2020). *Public Relations Review*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2020.101927>
- [15] Mangundjaya, Wustari L.H. Utoyo, Dharmayati B. Wulandari, Permata, (2015). The role of leadership and employee's condition on reaction to organizational change. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 172, pages 471-478.
- [16] Ms. J. SujaKannu, Ms. J. Vinodha Evangeline, K. Karthick, (2020). Impact of Covid19: Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) in Food Industry, India. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD) Volume 4 Issue 4, June 2020*. Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 6470
- [17] Opatha, H.H.D.P.J, (2020). COVID-19 in Sri Lanka and Seven HRM Related Recommendations against COVID-19. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, Vol 7, Issue 2, Pages 152-157.
- [18] R. van Dick, V. Ciampa, S. Liang, Shared Identity in Organizational Stress and Change, *COPSYC* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2017.11.005>
- [19] Sanders, Karin N., Phong T. Bouckenoghe, Dave R., Alannah S., Gavin, (2020). Unraveling the What and How of Organizational Communication to Employees During COVID-19 Pandemic: Adopting an Attributional Lens. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science* 1 –5.
- [20] Sasaki N, Kuroda R, Tsuno K, Kawakami N (2020). Workplace responses to COVID-19 associated with mental health and work performance of employees in Japan. *Journal of occupational health*, Volume 62, Issue 1, Page e2134.
- [21] Solis, Edgardo H., Ahmer B., Kai P., Henry J., Emma, (2020). Delayed emergency surgical presentation: impact of COVID19 on non-COVID patients. *ANZ Journal of Surgery*, <https://doi:10.1111/ans.16048>.
- [22] The Star 'covid-19-what does the new normal means? (2021)', available at: <https://www.thestar.com.my/lifestyle/health/2020/05/21/covid-19-what-does-the-039new-normal039-mean>.
- [23] Tyler, Tom R. De Cremer, David, (2005). Process-based leadership: Fair procedures and reactions to organizational change. *Leadership Quarterly*, Volume 16, Issue 4, Page 529-545.
- [24] Van D., Ciampa, S, (2018). Liang, Shared Identity in Organizational Stress and Change, *COPSYC*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2017.11.005>.
- [25] Wang, C., Cheng, Z., Yue, X. G., & McAleer, M., (2020). Risk management of COVID- 19 by universities in China. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13, 36-41.
- [26] Wolor, Christian W., Sholatia F., Ika, (2020). How to Manage Stress Experienced by Employees When Working from Home Due to the Covid-19 Virus Outbreak. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, Vol. 29, No. 5, (2020), pp. 8359-8364.